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EUROPEAN

POLICY BRIEF

Intersectionality: An in-depth focus

Authors: Rachel Palmén and the INSPIRE Consortium: see www.inspirequality.eu

Introduction and policy background

INSPIRE and aim of this policy brief

INSPIRE has been funded to create the European Centre of Excellence on Inclusive Gender Equality in Research & Innovation to provide thought leadership as well as build up a solid evidence base on inclusive gender equality plans (IGEPs). Four main challenges have been identified in the shift from “Gender Equality Plans” (GEPs) to “Inclusive Gender Equality Plans” (IGEPs): 1) how to sustain and deepen the momentum of change processes 2) the need to take a contextually sensitive, tailored approach to inclusive GEPs building on local knowledge, expertise and activism 3) the lack of know-how on integrating an intersectional perspective through GEPs 4) the lack of research and competences for inclusive gendered innovations. The specific aim of this policy brief is linked to the third challenge, to deepen an understanding of how to integrate an intersectional perspective into inclusive gender equality plans and policies in research organisations and innovation processes.

Intersectionality is understood as “a paradigm, theory, methodology, analytic or critical tool that focuses on the interlocking systems of oppression and privilege, power relations and social inequalities that occur along multiple axes including but not limited to gender, ethnicity and race, social and economic status, sexual orientation, disability and age” (Beeckmans et al., 2023). Intersectionality relates to the inseparability, interconnectedness, and interactions of multiple axes of privileges and disadvantages and is distinct from other concepts such as “inclusiveness” or “diversity” that are often invoked in gender equality and Equality Diversity Inclusion (EDI) interventions (see Palmén and the INSPIRE Consortium, 2023).

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Intersectional inequalities in Research & Innovation throughout Europe

A range of intersectional inequalities are clearly demonstrated by the latest Europe-wide statistics on gender equality in Research and Innovation (EC, 2025). The latest She Figures 2024 incorporates for the first time the EU's policy commitment to intersectionality by offering more detailed data on key indicators. It now includes disaggregated information on international mobility, employment conditions, and gender pay gaps in the higher education sector (HES).

Key findings include:

- Employment gaps by origin:
 - Tertiary-educated women born in their country of residence are more likely to work as highly skilled professionals in science and technology (HRSTCs) than those born in another EU Member State or outside the EU (73% vs. 63% and 58% respectively).
 - Underrepresentation in STEM roles: Women born outside the EU are significantly less likely to work as scientists or engineers (36%) compared to women from other EU countries (43%) and native-born women (42%).
 - Disability and employment: Among tertiary-educated individuals with disabilities, women are more likely to be employed as HRSTCs than men with similar qualifications.
- Working conditions and earnings:
 - The gender overall earnings gap (GOEG) widens with age in both scientific Research & Development (R&D) and the broader economy, pointing to increasing gender inequality in earnings over time.
- Career progression and leadership:
 - Most Grade A positions are held by individuals aged 55 and above, women make up just one-third of this group, highlighting persistent barriers to long-term career advancement.

This detailed picture leaves no doubt that taking an intersectional approach to tackling multiple inequalities in R&I is more necessary than ever.

Backlash against Science, Gender, Equality, Diversity and Inclusion

We are currently witnessing a backlash against science as well as against gender equality, diversity and inclusion interventions and policies. The global rise of far-right anti-gender politics and movements is challenging feminist socio-political progress, as well as the pursuit of gender equality and the rights of LGBTQIA+ individuals and people of colour (the global majority) (Hansalbin Sältenberg et al., 2024). Backlash is apparent in multiple ways across diverse national contexts. For example, in 2018 the Hungarian government officially removed Gender Studies Masters and PhD degrees from the list of accredited subjects. In Poland, in April 2021, the Polish Parliament passed a bill titled “Yes to Family, No to Gender,” advocating for Poland's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention—a significant treaty focused on addressing violence against women, including concerns like marital rape and female genital mutilation. In Serbia, research has shown how

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discourse from the anti-gender movement corresponds to broader activities of the international anti-gender movement (Stojčić & Bobičić, 2023). In Belgium we have seen the anti-gender mobilisations and threatening of trans-rights (Verlooy, 2024) whilst the European Network against Racism (ENAR) issued a statement “denouncing the escalation of attacks against Muslims and civil society organisations who work against racism and anti-Muslim hatred in France.”

In the United States we have seen the dismantling of Diversity Equality and Inclusion initiatives, the demonization of gender studies resulting in the derogatory denomination of “gender ideology” (Butler, 2024). Research projects “studying transgender populations, gender identity, diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) in the scientific workforce, environmental justice” funded by the United States National Institute for Health, are being terminated – as they no longer meet agency priorities (Kozlov & Mallapaty, 2025). These developments form part of a broader attack on democracy, academic freedom and science and must be contextualised as such.

In some countries, and regions, however Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion efforts in research and innovation are being given an impetus. For example, in India in 2025 the Office of Principal Scientific Adviser convened a consultation with experts to create a framework on “Diversity, Equity, Inclusion and Accessibility (DEIA) in Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics and Medicine (STEMM)”. In South Korea the Centre for Gendered Innovations of Science and Technology Research was founded in 2021. Whilst at a global level Nature Communications have put in place a whole number of actions on diversity and inclusion for internal and external operations. Tackling entrenched, multifaceted inequalities in research organisations must remain a top political and policy priority. Science cannot be excellent if multiple, complex inequalities remain unresolved, essentially excluding a large percentage of the potential talent base. Rapid advancements in technology and pressing environmental issues underscore the importance of broadening intersectional approaches within the realm of innovations (Nielsen et al., 2025).

Operationalising intersectionality

Effectively operationalising an intersectional approach into gender equality plans and equality policies to tackle multiple inequalities in R&I organisations is challenging for numerous reasons. Intersectionality tends to operate as an academic concept at a high level of abstraction whilst its practical application and its effective operationalisation into policy is a complex process (see Hankivsky, 2014). This is further exacerbated by the recognised need to develop evidence-based plans and interventions - and the observation that quantitative data collection on the range of protected characteristics is an infinitely complex and resource intensive endeavour (Müller & Humbert, 2025). Despite these challenges practitioners recognise a need to include and support diverse groups that are marginalised/under-represented. Thus, the theoretical concept is also very much a lived experience, recognised and acted upon even if practitioners do not necessarily refer to it as such. This INSPIRE policy brief tries to bridge some of

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these gaps and address some of these challenges and provide a useful framework so policy makers can advance this agenda.¹

Evidence and Analysis

Intersectionality: Legal, political and knowledge base

Work in INSPIRE demonstrates how legal and political frameworks for adopting an intersectional approach vary greatly throughout Europe (Caprile et al., 2023). For example, national experts' assessment of the current legal and political framework regarding its adequacy in fostering or sustaining significant advances in the field of (inclusive) gender equality in R&I organisations in each Member State vary from adequate to highly insufficient. In all EU 27 Member States "Adopting an intersectional approach" was seen as adequate in only 1 Member State (Germany); insufficient in 9; highly insufficient in 17 (Caprile et al., 2024; Warat et al., 2024).

This was also echoed by National experts' assessment of the current knowledge base on structural change in R&I organisations. We asked: is the current knowledge base adequate to support significant, evidence-based advances in the field of inclusive gender equality in R&I organisations? In all EU 27 Member States the current knowledge base for "Adopting an intersectional approach" is seen as highly adequate in 1 member State (Germany); insufficient in 10 Member States; and highly insufficient in 16 Member States (Caprile et al., 2023; Warat et al., 2024).

INSPIRE Gender Equality Plan monitoring survey and web scraping: Key findings

INSPIRE research demonstrates how the eligibility criterion has had a strong impact on the prevalence of GEPs throughout Europe. This is particularly true for those organisations that did not have a GEP before the start of Horizon Europe. Since 2020 there has been a significant increase in GEPs, 63% of organisations have adopted their first GEP whilst since 2021 significantly more organisations adopted a GEP for the first time than in previous years.² 37% of the organisations that set up a GEP stated they did so due to the Horizon Europe criterion. Evidence also highlights how some organisations that already had a GEP have adapted it to meet the requirements (Löther et al., 2024). This demonstrates that regulatory work

¹ This policy brief is the second of a series of four, this second brief is based on a) INSPIRE GEP prevalence and monitoring survey b) knowledge exchange event held in Vienna on the 27th of September 2024 – on intersectionality where we brought together INSPIRE consortium members, experts and CoP facilitators. As a result of this knowledge exchange event on Intersectionality four working papers were produced – one in each thematic area: Sustaining Change; Widening Participation, Intersectionality and Innovation. This Policy Brief aims to summarise these working papers and provide useful recommendations for policy makers in this area.

² 18% of the organisations adopted their first GEP in 2021 and 32% in 2022

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undertaken at the level of the European Commission to foster gender equality in research organisations is having a substantial impact.

This work needs to be deepened and extended to other axes of inequalities – through ensuring that GEPs take an intersectional approach. Research shows that most organisations still focus mainly on gender in their GEPs, with limited attention to broader diversity. Just 22% include diversity, and only 5% focus on broader inclusion. Diversity (80%) and inclusion (76%) as concepts however, are much more common than intersectionality (14%) in GEPs. GEPs that mention issues like race, class, nationality, or sexual orientation are more likely to adopt intersectional approaches. However, including religion tends to reduce this likelihood. Regarding non-binary identities, 35% of GEPs use terms like non-binary or trans whereas broader DEI or diversity-focused plans are much more likely to reflect non-binary perspectives (Karataş et al, forthcoming).

To truly advance equality, organisations must go beyond a binary concept of gender and consider multiple, overlapping dimensions of inequalities including race, disability, and gender identity. Supporting inclusive GEPs from an intersectional perspective is essential for building fair and equitable research environments.

Intersectionality: Cultivating intersectional practices and policies for equality work

Intersectionality as a “pure” academic concept – can be thought about as too complex to be effectively operationalised and implemented. The disjuncture, often highlighted in the academic literature, between what an “ideal”, comprehensive intersectional approach would look like compared to what is available in practice, leads to an assessment which inevitably falls short. This calls for a pragmatic strategy which is able to identify those policies and practices that are currently being developed, implemented and are impacting on intersections of inequalities. In effect as the INSPIRE case studies on intersectional policies have shown, most of those policies are characterised by two central features: 1) they are designed, implemented and/ or governed in ways that overcome siloed or single identity policy approaches, and 2) they address power inequalities (Van Laer et al., 2025).

Taking an inductive approach based on how RPOs and HEIs are developing and implementing intersectional policies, redefines this approach as a political strategy—as a pathway to achieving intersectional equity and social justice (Beeckmans et al., 2025). Intersectional policies, according to Christoffersen (2025), should aim to reduce overlapping inequalities and centre “the needs and/or improving the outcomes of those who are the most intersectionally disadvantaged”. This focus on operationalising intersectionality must remain central to its purpose.

Finally, it is crucial to share knowledge between different stakeholders (RFOs, RPOs, national authorities and the European Commission) about effective measures that have successfully reduced inequalities to inform and enhance future policy-making efforts.

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The following Box illustrates some examples of measures that have been developed to further intersectional equality in R&I organisations. They are taken from the INSPIRE working papers, Beeckmans et al, 2025 and Warat et al, 2025.

“Reverse’ mentoring (where for example, white people in senior positions of power are mentored by Black or racially minoritized colleagues in order to gain a deep understanding of and commitment to racial justice.” (Christoffersen in Beeckmans et al 2025).

“Positive and affirmative action (where those who have been systematically excluded are prioritized in order to improve equity and create a more level playing field to counteract systemic discrimination.” (Christoffersen, in Beeckmans et al 2025).

“Proper recognition of and remuneration for equity service work (for instance by incorporation into workload models and promotion criteria.” (Christoffersen, in Beeckmans et al 2025).

“Remuneration of the participation of those most intersectionality disadvantaged in policy development, implementation and evaluation.” (Christoffersen, in Beeckmans et al 2025).

“Create spaces to have difficult conversations (De Micheli, in Beeckmans et al 2025).

“Quota policies for vulnerable students of faculty, e.g. Afro-Americans in Brazil (Morgade, in Warat et al 2025).

“Exceptions or scholarship policies, e.g. bi- or multilingual policies (including sign language for hearing loss) in Argentinian Universities (Morgade, in Warat et al 2025).

“Return grants for early career female scientists to restart their careers after a parental break (IOCB, MendelU, MUNI) – combination of gender, age, caring responsibilities (Langhammerová, in Warat et al 2025).

Boot camp for international researchers, school assistant for children with different mother tongue language (IMG CAS) - combination of gender, age, caring responsibilities and ethnicity/ language. (Langhammerová, in Warat et al 2025).

Consideration of caring breaks in the evaluation procedure and in the grant process.” (Langhammerová, in Warat et al 2025).

For further initiatives see: www.advance-he.ac.uk/equality-charters/good-practice-initiatives

Sustaining change & intersectionality

The sustainable implementation of change initiatives involves understanding and addressing various forms of resistance, often stemming from those who benefit from existing power structures. Power dynamics play a pivotal role in shaping change, with intersectional equality frequently facing heightened pushback due to its challenge to entrenched privileges and inequalities. To advance such initiatives, it's essential to analyse these resistances, understand their root causes, and identify effective solutions and best practices for overcoming them. This approach helps ensure that change initiatives remain impactful and enduring.

Pathways for progress highlighted in the literature:

1. Overcoming resistance: Effective strategies include embedding gender and intersectionality within broader initiatives and connecting these efforts to funding mechanisms. This approach creates practical incentives for institutions to embrace and sustain meaningful change.

2. Facilitating change: Core principles like epistemic justice, care, and solidarity are essential in driving transformation and fostering inclusive practices.

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3. Valuing diverse contributions: Recognising the significance of teaching, service, and leadership alongside research is critical. Equally important is cultivating a deep understanding of inequality regimes and acknowledging the intersections of gender with other social categories.

4. Integrated interventions: Efforts to address inequalities must be seamlessly incorporated into the central strategies of research institutions, ensuring that they are not treated as isolated or secondary initiatives (Chaves et al., 2025).

Widening participation & intersectionality

The foundational principles of intersectionality, rooted in the experiences of Black women in the United States, have evolved and been adapted to diverse regional contexts worldwide, reflecting unique social, cultural, and political dynamics. In Latin America, intersectionality often centres around issues of race—particularly concerning Afro-Latin and Indigenous communities—alongside gender and class. These discussions frequently highlight the enduring effects of colonialism, economic exploitation, and ongoing struggles for indigenous rights and the recognition of Afro-descendant populations. In Central and Eastern Europe, the focus includes ethnic and national identities and disabilities, in addition to gender and socioeconomic status (Warat et al., 2025).

A crucial aspect of designing and implementing inclusive Gender Equality Plans is the collection of disaggregated data through a context-sensitive, intersectional approach. Analysing this data allows for the identification of specific barriers and disparities faced by various groups, enabling the development of targeted interventions, the evaluation of their effectiveness, and continuous improvement over time (Warat et al., 2025).

Innovation & intersectionality

Preliminary case study findings on research funders supporting and implementing (inclusive) gendered innovations presents notable challenges, particularly in integrating (inclusive) gendered innovation perspectives, fostering stakeholder engagement, and ensuring project sustainability. However, these obstacles can be addressed through targeted funding strategies, ongoing training, effective collaboration, and clear communication, paving the way for more inclusive and impactful innovations (Reidl et al., 2025). The following challenges in Funding Inclusive Gendered Innovations have been identified:

Communicating the rationale: Introducing (inclusive) gendered innovation funding programs presents a significant challenge for research funding organisations, particularly in effectively communicating their purpose. The limited awareness of (inclusive) gendered innovation within the applicant community often results in modest-quality initial applications (Reidl et al., 2025).

Evaluator expertise and consistency: The application of gender criteria across funding programs is inconsistent, with outcomes heavily reliant on the expertise of

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evaluators. Insufficient training in gender and intersectional issues among evaluators can lead to uneven assessments and a lack of depth in project evaluations.

Mainstreaming (inclusive) gendered innovation approaches: Funding organisations face obstacles in embedding (inclusive) gendered innovation perspectives meaningfully across all programs. While mainstreaming these approaches across various sectors can attract a broader pool of applicants, it may lead to less impactful and diluted projects. Conversely, targeted programs tend to achieve greater depth but often engage fewer applicants.

Policy implications and recommendations

Intersectionality offers potentially powerful leverage for creating alliances and building coalitions in favour of creating more inclusive research organisations (Woods et al., 2022; Christoffersen, 2024). INSPIRE takes a distributed and collaborative approach to knowledge production and practice, though supporting communities of practices of RPO's and RFO's working on inclusive gender equality and innovations. This approach must be extended and transcend different governance levels to foster collaboration between the European Commission, National Authorities, Research Funding Organisations, Research Performing Organisations and Higher Education Institutions.

European Commission:

- Data: The latest version of She Figures which integrates more indicators to highlight a range of inequalities, beyond gender is welcomed. Collecting context-specific yet comparable data regarding different socio-demographic characteristics such as ethnicity, race, gender, migration status etc. must be advanced if a range of intersecting inequalities in research organisations are to be successfully challenged (Müller & Humbert, 2025).
- Sustaining change: The role of the EU Commission in enforcing accountability for GEPs and extending their reach to tackle multiple inequalities is essential for progress. To maintain and extend the progress on gender equality in R&I, it is necessary to expand the current GEP policy framework by ensuring that an intersectional perspective is included. In line with ERA Subgroup 5 recommendations: IGEPs from an intersectional perspective must be made a permanent and integral element of EU research funding requirements to serve as a foundation for long-term sustainable improvements in gender equality and inclusiveness within the European R&I ecosystem.³

National authorities:

³ Advancing Inclusive Gender Equality: A Vision for Framework Programme 10: Position Paper on Framework Programme 10 from the ERA Forum Sub-Group 'Inclusive Gender Equality in the ERA'.

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- Intersectionality: National authorities ought to offer tailored guidance on implementing intersectional approaches to equality work that align with their specific national context. Such efforts should actively involve consultation with underrepresented groups. Although the development of intersectional strategies for gender equality may still be in its infancy, it is essential to integrate monitoring and evaluation processes when creating initiatives to address intersectional disparities.⁴

Research Funding Agencies:

- Early engagement and support: Reaching out to potential applicants early in the funding process and providing pre-application guidance enhances proposal quality. This approach helps applicants gain a clearer understanding of expectations for (inclusive) gendered innovations, ensuring their projects align more effectively with program objectives. (Reidl et al., 2025).
- Cross-sector collaboration: Partnerships between public institutions, private companies, and academia play a vital role in driving innovation. These collaborations promote the integration of (inclusiv Müller & Humbert, 2025 Müller & Humbert, 2025) gendered innovation principles and introduce diverse perspectives that enrich projects. (Reidl et al., 2025).
- Evaluator training and support: The success of funding programs relies on continuous training for evaluators. Offering ongoing support and engaging evaluators throughout the project lifecycle enhances the quality of assessments and ensures that projects achieve the required depth in integrating inclusivity into innovation. (Reidl et al., 2025).

Research Performing Organisations and Higher Education Institutions:

Intersectionality:

- Data collection: A self-declaration questionnaire allows individuals to voluntarily share identity-related information, helping organisations identify inequality and discrimination patterns. For example, see Stadler et al., (2023) who have developed the Diversity Minimal Item Set – which can be tailored to the organisation. For these tools to succeed, privacy concerns must be addressed by ensuring transparency about data collection's purpose, scope, and safeguards. Clearly communicating how data will be used to tackle structural inequalities can build stakeholder trust. Additionally, inviting feedback on the process through a post-implementation framework enhances transparency and demonstrates ethical commitment (Müller & Humbert, 2025; Beeckmans et al., 2025).
- Incorporating intersectionality into an organisation's mission and aligning it with institutional goals, such as social responsibility or sustainability amplify its relevance. By embedding intersectional principles into sustainability strategies or

⁴ In this section we reaffirm the Genderaction plus position paper, 2025: A New ERA for GEPs: National Level Monitoring and Evaluation (see https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/GAplus_PP_ANewERAforGEPs.pdf)

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other aligned objectives like human rights, organisations can build a strong case for transformative policies that effectively address intersecting inequalities. (Beeckmans et al., 2025).

Sustaining Change:

- Engaging privileged groups, particularly senior white men into strategies and action plans for inclusive gender equality from an intersectional perspective is crucial for gaining widespread institutional support. Understanding their motivations can help frame equality as a shared goal rather than a zero-sum game. Discussions about privilege and power often encounter resistance, as they challenge perceptions of personal achievement. However, embedding these conversations within research and capacity-building initiatives can foster constructive dialogue. A skilled facilitator is essential to guide such discussions, ensuring they result in actionable progress rather than defensiveness or backlash. (Chaves et al., 2025.)
- A strong bottom-up approach involves empowering academic and student communities to legitimize equality policies and foster change. Students hold significant influence as key stakeholders, with institutions often responding to their demands due to financial and reputational pressures. Activism—both within and outside institutions—is crucial, particularly in advancing the politics of care by ensuring that care work is properly valued, recognised, and equitably distributed. Proactive initiatives are needed to engage institutional actors in addressing marginalisation and driving sustained action. Additionally, drawing lessons from impactful social movements and tracing their influence on policy can provide valuable guidance for developing effective institutional strategies. (Chaves et al, 2025)

Widening Participation:

- Rather than creating a "checklist" of all potential discrimination variables to address universally, it is important to acknowledge that inequalities operate within specific contexts. The variables of discrimination to be considered must therefore be relevant and meaningful within the particular context, such as applying a decolonial approach in the case of Latin America (Bonder in Warat et al., 2025).
- Operational definitions: Research and theory often necessitate analysis and, at times, simplification to produce meaningful insights. However, real-world experiences are inherently situated and intricate. Intersectionality offers a powerful lens to deeply engage with people's lived realities, needs, and voices. We suggest approaching intersectionality through a situational and relational perspective, focusing on the specific practices of domination that emerge uniquely within different contexts (Morgado in Warat et al., 2025).

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